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6 **Comparative LCA of 1st and 2nd generation bio-isobutene as a drop-in substitute for fossil**

7 **isobutene**

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12 **Abbreviations**

ADP fossil	Abiotic Depletion Potential
AP	Acidification Potential
BDO	1,4-butanediol
CCUS	Carbon Capture Utilization & Storage
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
EP	Eutrophication Potential
ETBE	Ethyl-tertiary-butyl ether
FAETP	Freshwater Aquatic Ecotoxicity Potential
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HTP	Human Toxicity Potential

IBN	Isobutene
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LDPE	Low Density Polyethylene
MAETP	Marine Aquatic Ecotoxicity Potential
MTBE	Methyl-tert-butylether
ODP	Ozone Depletion Potential
PED	Primary Energy Demand
POCP	Photochemical Ozone Creation Potential
PP	Polypropylene
sc	scenario
TETP	Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

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4 **Abstract:**

5 Isobutene (IBN, C₄H₈) is widely used in industry. Currently, IBN production relies on
6 petrochemical processes. The current work assesses the comparative environmental
7 sustainability of bio-based IBN production routes based on 1st and 2nd generation sugar
8 compared to fossil IBN by applying the ISO 14044 based Life Cycle Assessment methodology.

9 In total nine scenarios are examined. Scenario 1 to 6 used 1st generation sugar for IBN
10 fermentation, the scenarios 7 to 9 use cereal straw based 2nd generation sugar. The scenarios

1 also differ in process energy source. The savings in Global Warming Potential (for 1st
2 generation IBN are up to 68% (scenario 1); for 2nd generation IBN, savings reach -105% if an
3 avoided burden approach for utilizing lignin as an energy source is applied (scenario 8). It is
4 found that applying renewable process energy is a prerequisite to maximize GHG-savings.
5 Special attention has to be drawn on the eutrophication potential, were none of the scenarios
6 show savings. This is driven by sugar crop cultivation due to fertilizer usage, thermal energy
7 from solid biomass or natural gas due to NO_x emissions, and nutrient use for fermentation (e.g.
8 ammonia). Scenario 4, 7 and 8 show savings for the acidification potential compared to fossil
9 IBN. A driver of acidification is biomass-based process energy generation mainly due to SO₂
10 and NO_x emissions from biomass combustion. In contrast, all scenarios show a better
11 environmental performance concerning FAETP, Abiotic Depletion and POCP. Process
12 development should focus on conversion efficiencies and fully renewable process energy
13 supply.

14 **Keywords:** bio-isobutene production, life cycle assessment, biorefining, bio-based drop-in
15 chemicals, 2nd generation sugar

16

17 1 **Introduction:**

18 To reach the Paris Agreement goal to keep global warming below 2 °C by the year 2100,¹ the
19 European Union (EU) issued the European Climate Law (2021/1119), which obligates climate
20 neutrality by 2050 by achieving net-zero greenhouse gas emissions for the EU countries as a
21 whole.² Currently, up to 90% of the feedstock used for organic chemistry products or process
22 energy in the chemical industry is of fossil origin.³ Accordingly, there is a need to accelerate
23 measures in the petrochemical and chemical industries to achieve significant greenhouse gas
24 (GHG) mitigation. In 2019 the GHG-emissions of chemical industry in the EU-27 made up
25 approx. 125 Mt CO₂-eq⁴, which is about 14 % of the EU-27 GHG-emissions reported for the total

1 industry sector (approx. 877 Mt)⁵. Although there has been a decrease of chemical industries
2 GHG-emissions of about 58% from 1991 to 2019 it is also a fact, that no more significant
3 emission reductions have been detected since 2013⁴, which underlines the need for strategies
4 to achieve further savings. In addition to avoiding fossil fuel emissions (e.g., by electrification),
5 carbon capture use and storage (CCUS), substituting fossil feedstocks with biomass, and
6 recycling chemicals are important cornerstones for climate change mitigation in this industrial
7 sector.⁶ The substitution of fossil-derived isobutene (IBN) with bio-based IBN is an example
8 of achieving a switch from fossil feedstock, contributing to de-fossilizing the chemical industry.
9 IBN, or isobutylene (C₄H₈), is the most important isomer among the four isomers of butene.⁷
10 Owing to its high reactivity with respect to addition and polymerization reactions, IBN is widely
11 used in the chemical industry. Today, butenes are obtained as co-products from cracking
12 processes in crude oil refining. IBN is contained in the C₄ stream from cracking processes, in
13 addition to the isomers of butene and butane, as well as multiple unsaturated C₄ hydrocarbons.⁸
14 Steam cracking processes are among one of the major GHG-emitters in chemical industry. The
15 production of 1 t of olefins is associated with the emission 1 t CO_{2eq}.⁹ There are several
16 downstream processing options to obtain IBN from the C₄ stream.

17 [Figure 1](#)

18 ~~Figure 1~~ summarizes the industrial pathways involved in fossil IBN production.

19 **Figure 1: Simplified overview of fossil IBN production processes^{7, 10}**

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21 Global IBN production is estimated to be approx. 30 million tons (t), of which 62% is generated
22 via fluid-catalytic cracking, 24% via steam cracking using liquid feeds, and 14% from isobutane
23 dehydrogenation. IBN is a versatile molecule that has several industrial applications. Some
24 exemplary applications are:

- 1 • downstream processing to methyl-tert-butylether (MTBE) or Ethyl-tertiary-butyl ether
2 (ETBE) as fuel additives using methanol or ethanol.
- 3 • Using isoprene to synthesize butyl-rubber
- 4 • Using p-cresol or 4-methoxyphenol to synthesize an antioxidant is formed.¹¹

5 Approx. 90% of the produced IBN volume is consumed for alkylate gasoline and
6 MTBE/ETBE production.¹² According to Bender, in 2014, approx. 10% of the IBN was
7 applied in chemical and butyl-rubber production. The yearly growth rate of IBN production
8 is estimated at 4%.¹² Taking into account global production, the estimated market growth
9 rate, and the versatile application potential, there is a huge potential for substituting fossil
10 IBN with a bio-based drop-in molecule, shifting towards decarbonizing the chemical
11 industry.

12 Bio-based products are not inherently environmentally sustainable or lead to GHG savings
13 compared to their fossil counterparts. The favorability of bio-based products depends on
14 multiple factors along the value chain. Examples include the type of renewable feedstock and
15 sourcing practices, production process design (e.g., choice of process energy sources), and
16 disposal options.¹³ Accordingly, it is important to derive a scientifically sound basis to assess
17 whether novel bio-based products achieve environmental benefits and GHG savings.¹⁴

18 Numerous studies have been conducted on LCA of different bio-based products and chemicals.
19 Zeilerbauer et al. (2021), who examined a wood-chip-based organosolv biorefinery, found that
20 although the biorefinery proved benefits in most impact categories, some had no benefits
21 compared to the reference products, which are propylene glycol, phenol and C6-sugar.¹⁵ Lask
22 et al. (2018), for example, clearly showed that the GHG mitigation potential of 2nd generation
23 bioethanol compared to fossil fuels depends on scenario assumptions such as biomass pre-
24 treatment technology and biomass yield, as well as carbon sequestration during feedstock
25 growth as this could add GHG-savings to the overall ethanol production pathway.¹⁶ In general,

1 the LCA of the 1st and 2nd generation sugar-to-bioethanol pathways has been broadly examined
2 in the literature and therefore provides comprehensive insights into environmental performance,
3 while other bio-based chemicals lack of recognition in LCA.¹⁷ Other bio-based chemicals have
4 also been investigated by applying LCA. Hermann et al. (2007), for example, examined the
5 GHG savings of 15 bulk bio-based bulk chemicals compared to their fossil counterparts. Adom
6 et al. (2014) conducted a similar study examining eight bio-based chemicals focusing on the
7 fossil energy consumption as well as emissions of propylene glycol, 1,3-propanediol, 3-
8 hydroxypropionic acid, acrylic acid, polyethylene, succinic acid, isobutanol, and 1,4-
9 butanediol. They found cradle-to-grave GHG-savings of 37% up to 86% depending on the
10 product.¹⁸ A study on direct fermentation of 1,4-butanediol (BDO) from wheat straw derived
11 sugars found approx. 60% GHG savings compared to fossil BDO and additional significant
12 savings in other impact categories.¹⁹ Another study assessed the environmental performance of
13 cellulosic isobutanol compared to ethanol and n-butanol production.²⁰

14 As shown in the previous paragraph displaying current literature there are numerous LCA of
15 various bio-based chemicals and materials Nevertheless the investigation of bio-based IBN
16 production pathways is currently lacking. To the best of our knowledge, there is only one study
17 available on the LCA of a biorefinery producing IBN via direct fermentation using an
18 engineered E. coli strain and xylo-oligosaccharides, which focuses on comparing two different
19 production locations, not accounting for the fossil benchmark product.²¹ van Leeuwen et al.
20 (2012) focus on the techno-economic assessment of fermentative IBN production ¹¹. Vela-
21 Garcia et al. (2020) performed an LCA of triisobutene, an oligomer of IBN, in terms of its
22 suitability for use as jet fuel. In contrast to previously reported studies on fermentative IBN
23 production, Vela-Garcia et al. (2020) examined the fermentation of wheat straw sugars to
24 isobutanol and subsequently obtained IBN via a dehydrogenation step. Finally, a GHG-saving
25 of 28% for bio-based triisobutene compared to conventional jet A1 is reported.²²

1 There is a research gap on a comprehensive LCA comparing direct IBN fermentation based on
2 1st and 2nd generation sugars comparing different sugar crops, sugar sources, process designs
3 and by-product handling options. The final comparison with fossil IBN derives conclusions on
4 the overall environmental favorability of the bio-based products. This support decision making
5 in two ways: 1. to give recommendations on bio-based IBN production route design and 2. to
6 provide evidence on the overall favorability of bio-based IBN compared to fossil IBN.

7 The novelty of the current work lies in comprehensively investigating the direct fermentation
8 of 1st and 2nd generation sugars to IBN using an engineered E. coli strain by applying LCA.
9 comparing it to the fossil IBN production routes. A newly developed route for direct IBN
10 fermentation is comprehensively investigated applying LCA. In contrast to similar works, the
11 foreground data for the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) of IBN fermentation is based on a realistic
12 biorefinery process design. The aim is to show the impacts of different technology setups and
13 scenario choices on the overall environmental performance of bio-based IBN production routes
14 and to provide recommendations for process optimization from an LCA perspective.

15 **2 Methodology**

16 LCA was conducted according to the ISO 14040:2006 and ISO 14044:2006 standards, which
17 define the basic structure and methodological procedures.²³ As LCA methodology is
18 comprehensively described in the literature and widely applied to different products and
19 processes^{24-31 32-35} no detailed description of LCA methodology is given here. The following
20 sections describe the goal and scope definition, Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) compilation, and
21 Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) of the bio-based IBN production system under study.

22 **2.1 Goal, Scope, and System boundaries**

23 The goal of this study was to conduct a full LCA for bio-based IBN production a) using 1st
24 generation sugar crops and b) using cereal straw (2nd generation sugar) as feedstock. A cradle-
25 to-gate system boundary was applied, encompassing all process steps from raw material

1 sourcing up to the final bio-based IBN at the factory gate ready for downstream processing.
2 The functional unit is the production of 1 kg of bio-based IBN. For IBN production, a black-
3 box approach was chosen instead of modelling each unit process. The black-box of 1st
4 generation IBN production comprises the fermentation of sugars using engineered E.coli and
5 purification of the gaseous fermentation product to obtain high-purity bio-based IBN. 2nd
6 generation IBN production comprises an additional process step of cereal straw pretreatment
7 (steam explosion) to obtain C5 and C6 sugars for fermentation. Feedstock pretreatment in this
8 case was also included in the black box of 2nd generation IBN production.

9 The system boundary for 1st generation IBN production is shown in [Figure 2](#)~~Figure 2~~. Sugar
10 beets and corn deliver thick juice, run-off, and glucose syrup as feedstock for IBN fermentation.
11 Thick juice is an intermediate of sugar production, which originates from the first evaporation
12 step, where the thin juice is concentrated to sugar content of 70%.³³ In contrast, run-off is a by-
13 product of sugar production that occurs from the downstream processing of thick juice. There
14 are several centrifugation and crystallization steps until the required crystal sugar output is
15 achieved. Run-off is a product of these centrifugation processes at the end of the beet sugar
16 production process chain.³⁴ Downstream processing of thick juice requires extra energy, which
17 is allocated to crystal sugar and run-off. According to experts from the sugar industry, 68% of
18 the additional energy demand is attributed to the final crystal sugar product and 32% to the run-
19 off, based on sucrose content. As no valuable by-products have been reported from IBN
20 fermentation and purification, no further allocation is applied. The environmental burdens are
21 fully attributed to the bio-based IBN as an end product.

22

23 **Figure 2: System boundary 1st generation IBN production**

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25 **Figure 3: System boundary 2nd generation IBN production**

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1 For 2nd generation IBN production, no environmental burden is attributed to the agricultural
2 cultivation of straw, except for the burdens arising from harvesting and transporting. In terms
3 of the Renewable Energy Directive (RED 2018/2001), ANNEX V C 18 specifies that straw,
4 along with other waste materials, should have zero life cycle emissions.³⁵ The impact of this
5 choice of methodology is discussed in the conclusion section. Lignin is a by-product of 2nd
6 generation IBN production and is used either for process energy production or as a substitute
7 for natural gas outside the IBN production system (avoided burden approach). Another
8 possibility is to apply an energy-based allocation approach to subdivide the lignin and IBN
9 production. All three approaches and their corresponding impacts on the results are presented
10 in this study.

11

12 In total, ten scenarios were examined: six for 1st generation IBN and four for 2nd generation
13 IBN (see [Table 1](#)). The scenarios differed in feedstock, sugar source, process energy
14 supply, and by-product utilization. The production location is assumed to be in an unspecified
15 EU country.

16 **Table 1: Scenarios examined.**

17

18 Concerning by-product utilization and the approaches to account for in LCA, Scenario 7 applies
19 an energy allocation approach based on the lower heating value (LHV) of IBN (44.8 MJ/kg)³⁶
20 and lignin (19.5 MJ/kg_{dry})³⁷. This resulted in an allocation factor of 38% for IBN and 62% for
21 the by-product lignin. In Scenario 8, it is assumed that all lignin is used for energy production
22 purposes outside the IBN production system and substitutes electricity and thermal energy from
23 natural gas elsewhere. Accordingly, an avoided burden approach was applied. Scenario 9
24 assumes on-site lignin utilization in Combined Heat and Power (CHP), which is designed to
25 meet the full steam demand (see [Table 2](#)). Due to the CHP design approach, the residual

1 electricity demand must be met using grid electricity. The assumed efficiencies reflect a CHP
2 with a total efficiency of 95% split into a $\eta_{th} = 76\%$ and $\eta_{el} = 19\%$ as an optimistic approach
3 representing modern CHP.³⁸ Based on a lignin output (on dry basis assuming a dry matter
4 content of 60%) of 3,710 kg/t_{IBN}, a total energy output of 73,960 MJ/t_{IBN} and an approximate
5 electricity output of 13,958 MJ/t_{IBN}, the thermal energy output of 55,680 MJ/t_{IBN} is assumed to
6 substitute energy from natural gas in the avoided burden approach.

7

8 The fossil benchmark process is a standard LCA database process (GaBi ts 10.6 Professional
9 database), which represents IBN production via the dehydrogenation of isobutane.³⁹ As
10 Lassacher et al. (2017) showed, there is a lack of reliable data for conducting an LCA of fossil
11 IBN. Therefore, there are several uncertainties in benchmarking with other fossil IBN
12 production,⁴⁰ thus benchmarking with standard LCA results is the most valid approach.

13 Table 2 shows an approximation of the lignin-based process energy supply with an on-
14 site CHP. Data were derived based on the basic production process.

15 **Table 2: Lignin utilization and process energy supply for Scenario 9.**

16 ^abased on 16bar saturated steam

17 ^b No residual lignin for potential off-site use; all lignin is fed to CHP.

18 ^c The lignin CHP alone is not sufficient to supply the total process energy needed; a proportion has to be supplied by offsite
19 facilities.

20

21 As shown in Table 2 the total thermal energy demand was supplied by lignin CHP. In
22 contrast approx. 43% of the electricity demand has to be supplied via the grid, as the lignin
23 CHP cannot meet the full electricity demand. For Scenario 8, the thermal energy production
24 from the total lignin output in a boiler was approximated in the avoided burden approach.⁴¹

25 The CML 2016 midpoint category methodology was applied to the LCIA.⁴² Characterization
26 and normalization were performed using LCA software GaBi ts 10.6, applying the latest set of
27 characterization factors.⁴³ The current work analyzed the impact categories listed in Table

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1 **Table 3: Analyzed impact categories.**⁴²

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3 In addition to the CML 2016 midpoint categories, the Primary Energy Demand (PED) was
4 analyzed for the scenarios. The renewable and fossil PED are discussed in Section 3.3.

5

6 **2.2 Life Cycle Inventory**

7 For 1st generation IBN production, foreground data on sugar beet cultivation, thick juice, and
8 run-off production are literature-based. The foreground data on the IBN fermentation and
9 purification step as well as the pretreatment and hydrolysis step for 2nd generation IBN
10 production were derived from the OPTISOICHEM basic process design (H2020 Grant
11 Agreement: # 744330).⁴⁴ The background data were obtained from the LCA databases GaBi ts
12 10.6 Professional and Ecoinvent 3.7.⁴⁸⁻⁴⁵ The LCA model was set up in GaBi ts 10.6
13 Professional software.⁴⁶ The applied background process is listed in the column “LCA database
14 dataset” in [Table 4](#) ~~Table 4~~ to [Table 5](#) ~~Table 5~~.

15 The LCI for sugar beet cultivation was taken from the BIOGRACE I – GHG-Emission
16 Calculation tool,³⁸ which is in the range of common LCI data reported in the literature on sugar
17 beet cultivation.⁴⁷⁻⁴⁸ The agricultural stage was modelled in GaBi ts 10.6 software.⁴⁶ Analogous
18 to sugar beet production, the LCI data for corn production were derived from the BIOGRACE
19 I – GHG-Emission Calculation tool.³⁸ Details on the LCI used for modelling the agricultural
20 cultivation of crops can be found in the supplementary material.

21

22 The LCI for thick juice production from sugar beets was compiled based on Vargas-Ramirez et
23 al. (2017), who set up a carbon footprint calculation for industrial beet sugars.⁴⁹ LCA databases
24 lack datasets referring to thick juice production; most standard datasets in LCA databases focus

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1 on molasses as a by-product of sugar production,⁵⁰ and not on intermediates such as thick juice.
2 For details on the used LCI to model thick juice production please refer to the supplementary
3 material.

4 As a by-product of thick juice downstream processing, the run-off is assumed to require
5 additional material and energy from several further centrifuging and crystallization steps.³⁴

6 Accordingly, the LCI for run-off production includes additional energy and material demand
7 resulting from centrifugation and crystallization. This simplification is due to the lack of
8 detailed LCI data on a process unit basis for sugar production. Data for beet sugar production
9 were obtained from Renouf et al. (2008).⁵¹ ~~Table 4~~ **Table 4** lists the additional inputs necessary
10 to obtain the runoff. For details on the LCI used to model run-off and sugar from corn
11 production please refer to the supplementary material.

12 ~~Table 4~~ **Table 4** shows the LCI for 1st generation IBN fermentation and purification. The data
13 represent basic production process data, which have been aggregated to mass and energy flows
14 entering and leaving the black box of fermentation and purification.

15 **Table 4: LCI for the production of 1 t of bio-based IBN based on 1st generation sugars.**

16 * If not stated otherwise, the dataset stems from the GaBi ts 10.6 Professional database

17 ~~Table 5~~ **Table 5** shows the LCI for 2nd generation IBN production. Again, the data has been
18 aggregated from the basic production process to represent a black box approach. The black box
19 in this case represents the pretreatment and hydrolysis of cereal straw to obtain sugars, IBN
20 fermentation, and purification.

21 **Table 5: LCI for the production of 1 t IBN based on 2nd generation sugars.**

22 ^abased on a total plant steam demand of 58t/h, ~230 °C and 2881 kJ/kgsteam

23 Based on the given LCI data for each of the ten scenarios, an LCA model was set up in the LCA
24 software GaBi ts 10.6. The processes from the databases applied to the LCA model are shown

1 in ~~Table 4~~ [Table 4](#) and ~~Table 5~~ [Table 5](#) as well as in the supplementary material. Based on this
2 process model, LCIA was run using the LCA software GaBi ts 10.6.

3 **3 Results**

4 **3.1 Life Cycle Impact Assessment**

5 Characterization and normalization according to the CML 2016 methodology were performed
6 using the LCA software GaBi ts 10.6. The impact categories analyzed in this study are shown
7 in ~~Table 3~~ [Table 3](#). The descriptive analysis of assessed midpoint categories did not follow the
8 weighting approach, as this is considered controversial.⁵²

9 **3.2 Greenhouse Gas Emissions**

10 Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions represent a “100-year Global Warming Potential
11 (GWP100)” according to CML 2001.⁴³

12 3.2.1 Biogenic carbon

13 The GWP100 did not account for biogenic carbon sequestration during sugar crop growth. The
14 biogenic CO₂-emissions from fermentation are assumed to be carbon neutral. Accordingly the
15 results in figure 4 and 5 are displayed without biogenic carbon. At the current demonstration
16 stage, the final end-user products of the IBN, such as ETBE, MTBE, butyl rubber used for tires,
17 or chewing gum production,¹¹ cannot be confirmed. The lifetimes of these products vary
18 substantially, so it is difficult to apply a suitable methodology (e.g. concerning the time aspect
19 of carbon bond) to account for biogenic carbon uptake. As Levasseur et al. (2013) stated, GHG-
20 emissions emissions must be multiplied by their respective GWP100 value and the time the
21 emission is released into the atmosphere relative to the 100-year assessment. The GHG
22 emissions strongly depend on the lifetime of a product over which stored biogenic carbon is
23 released into the atmosphere. CO₂ emissions occurring at time zero must be multiplied by 1,
24 emissions occurring after 50 years must be multiplied by 0.5, and emissions occurring after 100

1 years must be multiplied by 0.⁵³ Full biogenic carbon storage is only applicable where carbon
2 is stored in the product for at least 100 years. As there is currently no such scientific evidence
3 for bio-based IBN, biogenic carbon storage is not considered in this work. This assumption also
4 follows a recommendation from the European Association for Bioindustries, that only if there
5 is sufficient evidence to support the hypothesis that a material will remain stable for more than
6 100 years in a given product use or end-of-life scenario, then the carbon embodied in the product
7 shall be considered as sequestered permanently ⁵⁴Literature documents different approaches:
8 While e.g. Tonini et al (2021)⁵⁵ as well as Benavides et al (2020)⁵⁶ account for carbon uptake
9 in the LC for polymers, a recent report on the LCA of biopolymers issued by the Joint Research
10 Center of the European Commissions does not account for that effect of biopolymers ⁵⁷. So,
11 based on current literature both approaches seem to be appropriate.

12 Nevertheless, the following paragraph gives insights into the potential impact on GHG-
13 emissions, if carbon sequestration during sugar beet growth is considered. The CO₂ uptake by
14 the plant is estimated according to Nemecek et al (2015) by multiplying the carbon content in
15 the plant dry matter by the stoichiometric factor 44/12 ⁵⁸ CO₂ sequestration then is calculated
16 using stoichiometric factors. According to the stoichiometric factor bio-isobutene (C₄H₈)
17 contains 0,86 kg_{biogenic carbon}/kg_{IBN}. Applying the stoichiometric ratios $m_{CO_2} = (44/12) \times m_c$ the
18 carbon content in bio-IBN is equivalent to the sequestration of 3.14 kg of CO₂ in the final bio-
19 IBN. [Figure 4](#) summarizes the carbon balance for bio-IBN from sugar beets. So, if it is
20 accounted for carbon sequestration from a “cradle-to-gate” perspective 1 t of IBN theoretically
21 takes up 3.14 t CO₂. For a simplified biogenic carbon flow chart please see [Figure 4](#).

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Figure 4: Simplified carbon balance for 1 kg bio-IBN production based on sugar beets

3.2.2 Global Warming Potential results

Figur5 5 shows the GWP for 1st generation bio-based IBN production routes compared with fossil IBN production. Thus, the GHG savings strongly depend on the scenario. The highest saving for 1st generation IBN production is found in Scenarios 4 and 5, which show a GWP savings of approximately. 62% and 63% compared to fossil IBN. The savings of Scenarios 1, 2, 3, and 6 show significantly lower savings in the range of 16% for Scenario 3 and approximately 33% and respectively 32 % for Scenarios 1 and 6. Within the scenarios for 2nd generation IBN, Scenario 8 shows the highest savings owing to an avoided burden approach. Scenario 9 shows GHG savings of approx. 70% compared to fossil IBN. Scenario 7 was the only scenario that showed an increase in GWP by 50 %. Details on the contribution of unit processes to the GWP can be found in [Figure 5](#) and [Figure 6](#) for 1st and 2nd generation IBN production.

Figure 5: GWP of 1st generatio bio-based IBN production compared to fossil production without biogenic CO₂*

*the category "others summarizes unit processes fo auxiliary materials and transport operations which show a minor contribution the overall GWP.

Figure 6: GWP of 2nd generatio bio-based IBN production compared to fossil production without biogenic CO₂*

*the category "others summarizes unit processes fo auxiliary materials and transport operations which show a minor contribution the overall GWP.

The choice of process energy has a significant impact on the overall results. Scenarios with total renewable energy supply (electricity and steam from biomass), such as Scenarios 4, 5, , show the highest GHG savings compared to the fossil route. In scenario 4 and 5 process energy generation only makes up 5 % of the total GWP: In contrast to that, in scnearios 1, 2, 3 and 6 the EU28 electricity mix shows a contribution of 48 % and in scenario 3 an additional GWP of

1 27 % from steam generation using natural gas is evident. Auxiliary materials and transport
2 operations which are summarized in the category “other” show only a minor contribution to the
3 GWP of 3 %.

4 In the case of 2nd generation IBN production, the methodology also impacted the results.
5 Although Scenario 8 applies a European electricity mix and natural gas as a process energy
6 source, the saving is still high as lignin substitutes thermal energy from natural gas off-site.
7 Applying the same process energy mix, but assuming an energy-content-based allocation
8 between IBN and the by-product lignin, leads to a significantly higher GWP in Scenario 7. As
9 shown in ~~Figure 6~~ Figure 6 choosing the avoided burden approach has a high impact on the
10 overall result in scenario 8. Scenario 8 profits from the assumptions that the lignin is used for
11 electricity and thermal energy generation in order to substitute natural gas leading to a
12 significant GHG emission credit. In contrast there is no justification for such a credit in scenario
13 9 as all the lignin is used in an on-site CHP; a small amount of electricity still has then to be
14 taken from the grid, which adds GHG-emissions. Scenario 7 represents the most conservative
15 approach applying process steam from natural gas for IBN production and subdividing GHG-
16 emissions between the main product IBN and the by-product lignin applying energy content
17 based allocation. In addition to process energy generation, sugar production is a major
18 contributor to IBN production. In Scenarios 1 to 5, sugar production makes up between 37 %
19 for thick juice and 39 % for run-off. The impact if run-off production is slightly higher as it is
20 a product of downstream processed thick juice. In scenario 6 sugar production makes up for
21 approx. 25 %. Primary Energy Demand

22 The PED reflects GWP savings. Except for Scenario 7, PED savings were found for all bio-
23 based IBN production scenarios. The savings for 1st generation IBN ranged from approx. 21%
24 in Scenario 2 up to 42% in Scenario 4. Second generation IBN production also leads to PED

1 savings compared with fossil IBN, except for Scenario 7. The highest savings were observed in
2 Scenario 8 with approx. 54%.

3 **Figure 7: Comparison of Primary Energy Demand for 1st and 2nd generation bio-based isobutene production**
4 **compared to fossil production**

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7 Process energy demand and sugar production are the main contributors to the overall PED. In
8 addition to the overall process energy savings compared to fossil IBN, another advantage of
9 bio-based IBN is an increase in renewable PED. While fossil IBN production shows marginal
10 renewable PED, the renewable share of PED among the bio-based production routes is up to
11 62% in Scenario 9, where lignin is used for process energy generation.

12 **3.3 Other Environmental Impact Categories**

13 As reducing GHG emissions is the most important measure to limit climate change,⁶ the carbon
14 footprint of products has become a core benchmark for assessing a product's favorability
15 compared to a (fossil) alternative. Accordingly, other environmental benchmarks are not
16 reflected in current policies as they focus on defining decarbonization goals or in setting GHG-
17 saving targets for specific products.^{35,59} To provide a more holistic view of the environmental
18 sustainability of bio-based IBN production routes, the full set of impact categories within the
19 CML 2001 methodology (see [Table 3Table-3](#)) was analyzed. For the 1st generation IBN
20 production scenarios (Scenarios 1–6) four major contributors to environmental impacts can be
21 identified, contributing approx. 35%- 100%, depending on the impact category. These four
22 mass and energy flows are sugar beet cultivation, production of sugar source (thick juice, run-
23 off, glucose syrup from corn), process steam, and electricity grid mix. Other auxiliaries are
24 minor contributors to environmental impacts. Depending on the scenario sugar beet cultivation,
25 production of sugar source, process steam, and electricity grid mix were responsible for 92%-

1 95% of the Acidification Potential (AP), 78%-83% of the Eutrophication Potential (EP), 43%-
2 64% of the Freshwater Aquatic Ecotoxicity Potential (FAETP), 87 %-90% of the Human
3 Toxicity Potential (HTP), 77% -96% of the Marine Aquatic Ecotoxicity Potentials (MAETP),
4 35%-57% of the Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP), approx. 100% of the Photochemical Ozone
5 Creation Potential (POCP), and 77%-93% of the TETP in 1st generation IBN production
6 scenarios. In ODP, a further 43%-65% was related to the use of potassium hydroxide, sulfuric
7 acid, and hexane.

8 For the 2nd generation IBN production scenarios, greater differences were found in the
9 contributors. As expected, the largest difference was found in Scenario 7 applying the EU-28
10 electricity mix and natural gas as the process energy, and Scenario 9, which uses lignin for a
11 100% renewable process energy supply. In Scenario 7, the major contributor to the
12 environmental impact categories was the EU-28 electricity mix and process steam from natural
13 gas. These two energy flows are responsible for 90% of the Abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP),
14 81% of the AP, 52% of the EP, 81% of the HTP, 73% of the MAETP, 85% of the POCP, and
15 66% of the TETP. A further approx. 20% of the EP and approx. 14% of the FAETP is
16 contributed by wastewater treatment. In Scenario 9, the lignin CHP together with wastewater
17 treatment and sulfuric acid use accounted for approx. 62% of the ADP, 80% of the AP, 66% of
18 EP, 54% of FAET, 89% of HTP, 96% of MAETP, 87% of POCP, and 86% of TETP. The
19 negative POCP for the truck transport process is a phenomenon that has only been reported
20 using the CML LCIA methodology in GaBi ts 10.6. The negative POCP is caused by the
21 division of the NO_x emissions into the two single emissions NO₂ and NO which has been
22 implemented from GaBi ts 5/6 versions onward. For the NO a negative effect on the POCP is
23 reported since it reduces the close ground ozone formation. Although it is a physical correlation
24 the message of “cleaning the air by driving a truck” is questionable.⁶⁰ This must be considered
25 when interpreting the results.

1 As with GWP, the final result depends closely on the scenario and on whether an environmental
2 improvement is achieved by bio-based IBN vs. fossil IBN. The environmental benefits of bio-
3 based IBN could not be determined for every impact category. For the impact categories ODP,
4 EP as well as MEAP and TEP the bio-based production routes show now benefits compared to
5 fossil IBN. Significant savings compared to the fossil fuel production route in most
6 environmental impact categories were found for scenarios 4 and 8. Across all scenarios, the
7 major environmental hotspots i.e. processes and activities that have the greatest contribution to
8 the total environmental impact were the AP, EP, MAETP, ODP, and TEP. In the case of the
9 AP, major contributors include the EU electricity grid mix and process steam from biomass
10 (Scenarios 1 and 2), electricity from biomass, and process steam from biomass (Scenarios 3, 4,
11 and 5).

Table 6: Environmental impact savings of bio-based IBN production compared to fossil IBN production (100% = fossil IBN).

1 Auxiliary inputs such as chemicals and other operating materials play a minor role in
2 environmental performance.

3 **4 Discussion**

4 A limitation in comparing fossil IBN and 1st and 2nd generation IBN production routes is that
5 they show completely different technology readiness levels (TRLs). The processes for 1st
6 generation and even more 2nd generation IBN are not mature, and there is still room for process
7 improvements, especially in terms of conversion efficiency and process integration. Figure 7
8 and 8 show parameter variation for 1st and 2nd generation IBN production. For 1st generation
9 IBN the sugar demand is varied from -50% to +50% which has not only an impact on the
10 process stage of sugar production, but also on sugar beet cultivation. A decreasing specific
11 sugar demand can be achieved by increased fermentation efficiencies. As shown in [Figure](#)
12 ~~8~~[Figure-8](#) this is an appropriate measure to lower overall specific GHG-emissions from IBN
13 fermentation.

14 **Figure 8: Potential impact on GWP of -50% to +50% sugar demand for the production of 1st generation** 15 **bio-based IBN production**

16 For 2nd generation IBN the parameter of straw demand and IBN yield are chosen for parameter
17 variation. Again, a theoretical decrease of -50% and increase of +50 % is assumed for both
18 parameters. An increase in specific IBN yield based on a given straw input (t_{IBN}/t_{straw}) leads to
19 a decrease of process energy demand. Process steam demand of pretreatment and hydrolysis
20 decreases as less straw needs to be processed for achieving the same IBN output and in case of
21 fermentation of purification less steam is demanded to produce a higher amount of IBN. As
22 shown in [Figure 9](#)~~Figure-9~~ especially process development to decrease straw demand can be
23 recommended as pretreatment and hydrolysis show a higher process steam demand and in line
24 higher GHG-emissions.

25 **Figure 9: Potential impact on GWP of -50% to +50% IBN yield.**

26 LCA applied to process design can identify major environmental hotspots. Generally, the earlier
27 the decisions on process design are made, the greater the impacts on future environmental
28 performance.⁶¹ For bio-based IBN production, the following recommendations for further
29 process development are derived:

- 30 • Applying renewable process energy (electricity and process steam) is a prerequisite for
31 achieving a favorable GHG balance.
- 32 • In the case of 2nd generation IBN production, the use of lignin for process energy
33 purposes is recommended to achieve a favorable overall environmental performance.
- 34 • If lignin is not used for process energy purposes, it should be utilized off-site as an
35 energy source to justify calculating credits for the substitution of fossil energy sources.
- 36 • Sugar crop cultivation and sugar feedstock production are major environmental impact
37 contributors and increasing fermentation efficiencies to lower the specific sugar demand
38 is key to improving environmental performance.
- 39 • Pretreatment and hydrolysis are energy-consuming steps in obtaining fermentable
40 sugars. Therefore, increasing the fermentation efficiency for 2nd generation IBN is key
41 to improving the environmental performance of 2nd generation IBN.
- 42 • In addition, wastewater treatment, as well as the use of auxiliary chemicals such as
43 sulfuric acid, hexane, and ammonia, can be optimized to realize additional
44 environmental benefits. In particular, where process energy is generated from renewable
45 resources, optimizing material uses is important in improving environmental
46 performance.

47 In the long term, considering the decarbonization target for the year 2050 in the EU,⁶² the use
48 of fossil process energy must be phased out. Accordingly, the scenarios applying fully
49 renewable process energy are representative of future bio-based value chains.

50

51 In contrast, fossil IBN production is a fully mature process, and refineries have been optimized
52 for decades to be as efficient as possible and to maximize product output.⁶³ This fact hampers
53 the comparability of LCA results and is also the reason the why not for environmental impact
54 categories and all biobased IBN production scenarios savings compares to the fossil products
55 are found. It is often reported that, when applying a cradle-to-gate perspective, bio-based
56 products do not lead to environmental benefits, at least in some impact categories, compared to
57 their fossil counterparts.^{47,64}

58 Several aspects can maximize the environmental performance of bio-based products (non-
59 exhaustive list): valorization of underutilized residue biomass, use of renewable process energy,
60 improvement of biomass conversion efficiencies, short transport distances, applying biorefinery
61 concepts and comprehensive by-product valorization, include the end-of-life to LCA.
62 Comparison of bio-based products with fossil products in LCA has already been discussed, and
63 limitations include the use of fossil benchmarks to account for best practices, lack of
64 transparency in LCI data, and the use of data provided by industry. A relevant claim is that the
65 use of renewable carbon instead of fossil carbon has an inherent value that should be considered
66 in environmental assessments.⁶⁵ As Benavides et al (2020) found, the carbon uptake during
67 biomass growth is one of the major benefits of biobased materials, which also leads to
68 significant GHG-emissions savings compared to their fossil counterparts⁵⁶. Also, in the current
69 study the accounting for biogenic carbon uptake in the bio-based IBN potentially leads to even
70 more significant GHG-savings compared to fossil IBN (see also section 3.2.1).

71 In most cases for fossil product benchmarks are used from LCA databases the detailed LCI is
72 not available due to confidentiality issues. Accordingly the LCA results for the benchmark are
73 not fully understandable or reproducible. In some cases this data represents state-of-the Art
74 technology missing any information on the proportion of petrochemical plants in a given

75 geographical region really operating according to this modern state-of-art assumptions. Values
76 for non- state of the art plants are mostly not available. Due to a lack of literature based LCI
77 data on petrochemical processes a reproduction of these processes is not possible in most cases.
78 Further, comparing TRL 9 petrochemical processes with TRL 5-7 (or lower) bio-based
79 processes leads to distortions in results and interpretation.

80

81 **5 Conclusions:**

82 Bio-based IBN made from 1st generation sugar shows GHG-savings compared to fossil IBN of
83 up to 62%, if renewable process energy is applied. This cradle-to-gate saving may be even
84 higher, if it is accounted for the biogenic carbon uptake during biomass growth which becomes
85 evident in section 3.2.1. 2nd generation bio-based IBN – assuming straw as an agricultural
86 residue as sugar feedstock – shows a GHG-saving of up -129% if an avoided burden approach
87 for the lignin as a by-product is chosen. Bio-based IBN shows significant savings in other
88 environmental impact categories too, e.g. in the Abiotic Depletion Potential, Freshwater
89 Aquatic Ecotoxicity Potential or the Photochemical Ozone Creation Potential, just to name
90 those which show savings for all bio-based scenarios.

91 Additionally, bio-based IBN provides further advantages compared to its fossil counterpart,
92 which are not directly shown in the LCA:

- 93 • Developing and establishing value chains for bio-based chemical production is a
94 prerequisite for establishing a bioeconomy and therefore supports the European
95 Bioeconomy Strategy.^{66,67}
- 96 • Producing chemical building blocks from domestic bio-based resources reduces fossil
97 resource and import dependencies.⁶⁸
- 98 • When using cereal straw for bio-based IBN production, the trade-off between food and
99 fuel is mitigated, especially if the sustainability criteria for straw removal from the field
100 are respected.^{69,70}
- 101 • The use of agricultural residues is not associated with additional GHG emissions or
102 other negative environmental and social effects from land-use change.⁷¹

103 Although LCA has proven to be a strong decision support tool in process design, the benefits
104 and burdens of bio-based IBN do not end with the quantitative analysis of environmental
105 impacts. Therefore, accompanying approaches such as a Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
106 (LCSA), which also includes social and economic aspects,⁷²⁻⁷³ are recommended to provide a
107 more holistic view.

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113

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350 **Table 1: Scenarios examined.**

Scenario	Feedstock	Sugar stream	Location	Product	Process energy electricity	Process energy steam	By-product	By-product utilization
Sc. 1	Sugar beet	Thick juice	EU	IBN	EU-28 electricity mix	Biomass/straw- CHP & natural gas boiler	None	-
Sc. 2	Sugar beet	Run-off	EU	IBN	EU-28 electricity mix	Biomass/straw-CHP & natural gas boiler	None	-
Sc. 3	Sugar beet	Thick juice	EU	IBN	EU-28 electricity mix	Natural gas CHP & natural gas boiler	None	-
Sc. 4	Sugar beet	Thick juice	EU	IBN	electricity from biomass	Biomass/straw-CHP & natural gas boiler	None	-
Sc. 5	Sugar beet	Run-off	EU	IBN	electricity from biomass	Biomass/straw-CHP & natural gas boiler	None	-
Sc. 6	Corn	Glucose syrup	EU	IBN	EU-28 electricity mix	Biomass/straw-CHP & natural gas boiler	None	-
Sc. 7	Cereal straw	Hydrolysate	EU	IBN	EU-28 electricity mix	Natural gas	Lignin	Off-site (allocation)
Sc. 8	Cereal straw	Hydrolysate	EU	IBN	EU-28 electricity mix	Natural gas	Lignin	Off-site (credit)
Sc. 9	Cereal straw	Hydrolysate	EU	IBN	lignin-CHP/EU-28 electricity mix	Lignin-CHP	Lignin	On-site

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352 **Table 2: Lignin utilization and process energy supply for Scenario 9.**

	Unit	Basic production case
Steam demand^a IBN production	MJ _{steam} /tIBN	44,559
Lignin input to CHP	MJ _{lignin} /kgIBN	73,480
Electricity demand	MJ _{el} /tIBN	24,510
Excess lignin for off-site use^c	MJ _{lignin} /tIBN	0 ^b
Thermal energy from lignin from CHP	MJ _{th} /tIBN	44,559
Electricity from lignin from chp^b	MJ _{el} /tIBN	13,958
Electricity demand from grid	MJ _{el} /tIBN	10,555^c

353 ^abased on 16bar saturated steam354 ^b No residual lignin for potential off-site use; all lignin is fed to CHP.355 ^c The lignin CHP alone is not sufficient to supply the total process energy needed; a proportion has to be supplied by offsite facilities.

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359 **Table 3: Analyzed impact categories.**⁴²

CML 2016 impact categories	Unit
Global warming potential (GWP 100 years)	[kg CO ₂ -Equiv.]
Ozone depletion potential (ODP, steady state)	[kg R11-Equiv.]
Acidification potential (AP)	[kg SO ₂ -Equiv.]
Eutrophication potential (EP)	[kg Phosphate-Equiv.]
Photochemical ozone creation potential (POCP)	[kg Ethene-Equiv.]
Human toxicity potential (HTTP inf.), Terrestrial ecotoxicity potential (TETP inf.)	[kg DCB-Equiv.]
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity potential (FAETP inf.), Marine aquatic ecotoxicity potential (MAETP inf.)	[kg DCB-Equiv.]
Abiotic depletion potential (ADP)	[kg Sb-Equiv.]

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362 **Table 4: LCI for the production of 1 t of bio-based IBN based on 1st generation sugars.**

Input	Value	Unit	LCA database dataset *
Sugar (thick juice, run-off)	3,760.0	kg	Literature based set up. For details please see the tables in the supplementary material.
ammonia	25.7	kg	Ammonia (NH ₃); Haber- Bosch- Process, from natural gas, including primary production; production mix, at plant; 0.86 kg/m ³ , 17,031 g/mol (en)
phosphoric acid (H ₃ PO ₄)	3.5	kg	Phosphoric acid (H ₃ PO ₄ , 54% P ₂ O ₅); acid digestion of phosphate rock, including primary production; production mix, at plant; 54% (en)
Di-Ammonium-Phosphate (DAP) 18% N 46% P ₂ O ₅	7.7	kg	Diammonium phosphate (DAP, 18% N, 46% P ₂ O ₅); neutralizing phosphoric acid with ammonia, including primary production; production mix, at plant; 18% nitrogen, 46% phosphate (en)
Potassium hydroxide (KOH)	3.2	kg	<u>Ecoinvent</u> ; potassium hydroxide production potassium hydroxide Cutoff, U (Europe)
Ammonium sulphate (AS)	3.3	kg	Ammonium sulphate (Caprolactam production); propene ammoxidation; production mix, at plant; solid, density: 1,77 g·cm ⁻³ , molar mass: 132,14 g·mol ⁻¹ (en)
Average K ₂ O fertilizer (kg K ₂ O)	0.5	kg	Potassium chloride (KCl/MOP, 60% K ₂ O); shaft mining and beneficiation, including primary production; production mix, at plant; 60% potassium content (en)
Sulfuric acid (H ₂ SO ₄)	0.2	kg	Sulfuric acid mix (96%); technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; 96% aqueous solution, M = 98.079 g/mol (en)
Magnesium oxide	0.1	kg	<u>Ecoinvent</u> ; magnesium oxide production magnesium oxide Cutoff, U (Europe)
Nitrogen	19.1	kg	Nitrogen (liquid); via cryogenic air separation; production mix, at plant; 14.0 g/mol (en)
n-hexane for purification	0.8	kg	Isohexane production isohexane Cutoff, U (Europe)
Water	17.6	m ³	
Electricity	1,930.0	kWh	Electricity grid mix; AC, technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; < 1kV (en) FR
Steam-biomass CHP (wheat straw)	1,637.0	kWh	Process steam from biomass (solid) 85%; technology mix regarding firing and flue gas cleaning; production mix, at heat plant; MJ, 85% efficiency (en)
Natural gas – 4,000 km, EU mix	143.0	kWh	Natural gas mix, EU-28

363 * If not stated otherwise, the dataset stems from the GaBi ts 10.6 Professional database

Table 5: LCI for the production of 1 t IBN based on 2nd generation sugars.

Input	Value	Unit	LCA database dataset
Wheat straw	9.0	t/t _{IBN}	Cereal straw is assumed to be a residue; no allocation of inputs/outputs to straw - all are attributed to the grain ³⁵
Electricity	6,809.0	kWh/t _{IBN}	EU-28: Electricity grid mix; AC, technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; <1kV (en) Lignin-CHP according to basic process design
Steam (16 barg)^a	44,559.0 ^a	MJ/t _{IBN}	EU-28: Process steam from natural gas 90%; technology mix regarding firing and flue gas cleaning; production mix, at heat plant; MJ, 90% efficiency EU-28: Process steam from biomass (solid) 90%; technology mix regarding firing and flue gas cleaning; production mix, at heat plant; MJ, 90% efficiency Lignin-CHP according to basic process design
Natural gas	29.0	kWh/t _{IBN}	EU-28: Natural gas mix; technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; medium pressure level (< 1 bar) (en)
Instrument air	424.0	m ³ /t _{IBN}	EU-28: Compressed air; 7 bar, high efficiency; production mix, at plant; low electricity consumption (en)
Water	2,866,220.0	kg/t _{IBN}	EU-28: Tap water from groundwater; filtration, disinfection, ion removal, etc., from groundwater; production mix, at plant; 1000 kg/m ³ , 18 g/mol (en)
Nitrogen	8.0	m ³ /t _{IBN}	EU-28: Nitrogen (gaseous); via cryogenic air separation; production mix, at plant; 1.250 kg/m ³ , 14.0 g/mol (en)
Urea	28.0	kg/t _{IBN}	EU-28: Urea (46% N); from ammonia and carbon dioxide, including primary production; production mix, at plant; 46% nitrogen content (en)
NaOH	221.0	kg/t _{IBN}	EU-28: Sodium hydroxide (caustic soda) mix (100%); technology mix; production mix, at plant;
H₂SO₄	44.0	kg/t _{IBN}	DE: Sulfuric acid mix (96%); technology mix; consumption mix, to consumer; 96% aqueous solution, M = 98.079 g/mol
Yeast extract	35.0	kg/t _{IBN}	Yeast has been modelled according to data in GREET
Phosphoric acid	4.0	kg/t _{IBN}	EU-28: Phosphoric acid (H ₃ PO ₄ , 54% P ₂ O ₅); acid digestion of phosphate rock, including primary production; production mix, at plant; 54% (en)
Ammonia	146.0	kg/t _{IBN}	EU-28: Ammonia (NH ₃); Haber- Bosch- Process, from natural gas, including primary production; production mix, at plant; 0.86 kg/m ³ , 17.031 g/mol (en)
ISOPAR V	0.3	kg/t _{IBN}	Cut-off
FeCl₃ (41% wt)	5.0	kg/t _{IBN}	Cut-off
CaO	101.0	kg/t _{IBN}	Lime (CaO; quicklime lumpy); calcination of limestone; single route, at plant; 3.34 g/cm ³ , 56 g/mol (en)

365 ^abased on a total plant steam demand of 58t/h, ~230 °C and 2881 kJ/kgsteam

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367 **Table 6: Environmental impact savings of bio-based IBN production compared to fossil IBN production (100% = fossil IBN).**

Impact category	Unit	Sc1	Sc2	Sc3	Sc4	Sc5	Sc6	Sc7	Sc8	Sc9
ADP fossil	[MJ/t _{IBN}]	-69%	-54%	-60%	-79%	-69%	-66%	-19%	-104%	-77%
AP	[kg SO ₂ eq./t _{IBN}]	61%	118%	33%	-20%	65%	68%	-1%	-97%	72%
EP	[kg Phosphate eq./t _{IBN}]	158%	282%	103%	55%	225%	130%	141%	149%	408%
FAETP inf.	[kg DCB eq./t _{IBN}]	-55%	-51%	-61%	-61%	-38%	-38%	-69%	-29%	-29%
GWP 100 years	[kg CO ₂ eq./t _{IBN}]	-33%	-31%	-16%	-65%	-66%	-33%	57%	-106%	-55%
HTP inf.	[kg DCB eq./t _{IBN}]	-14%	5%	-29%	-68%	23%	-8%	-45%	-76%	30%
MAETP inf.	[kg DCB eq./t _{IBN}]	885%	920%	87%	-18%	2575%	948%	122%	-43%	2922%
ODP, steady state	[kg R11 eq./t _{IBN}]	1.5*10 ⁶	1.0*10 ⁶	1.5*10 ⁶	1.8*10 ⁶	1.0*10 ⁶	2.2*10 ⁶	0.3*10 ⁶	0.9*10 ⁶	0.9*10 ⁶
POCP	[kg Ethene eq./t _{IBN}]	-81%	-79%	-87%	-95%	-72%	-77%	-82%	-100%	-67%
TETP inf.	[kg DCB eq./t _{IBN}]	106%	132%	-16%	-39%	290%	167%	269%	142%	614%

	saving
	no saving

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